

PROCEEDINGS

Virtual International Conference

on

Multidisciplinary Research-2022

[VICMR-2022]

01-05-2022

**Jointly Organized
by**

**Association of Global Academicians and
Researchers (AGAR)**

&

**Association of Indian Biologists (AIB)
Tamil Nadu, India**

ISBN: 978-93-94198-04-3

**Proceedings of
Virtual International Conference on
Multidisciplinary Research-2022
[VICMR-2022]**

**Jointly Organized by
Association of Global Academicians and
Researchers (AGAR)
and
Association of Indian Biologists (AIB),
Tamil Nadu, India**

ISBN: 978-93-94198-04-3

Date: 01-05-2022

Study of Customer Aspects of Cyber Securities in E-Banking

Dr. Atul Kumar¹, Anubhav Tiwari², Jai Mantri³, Debankur Chakraborty⁴

¹Professor, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, India

^{2,3,4}Student, Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School, Pune, India

Abstract:

The Internet seems to be the new delivery channel in the banking sector. Factors such as the security of personal data or the reliability of a financial institution have been identified as the determinants of electronic-banking adoption. In this paper, we have tried to analyse customers perception and awareness towards e-banking, problems faced by them while using e-banking along with security and privacy concern faced by them. A series of new factors, such as the difficulties of using the Internet, are shown to play a crucial role in the consumer's attitude – adoption or rejection – of this new alternative channel.

Keywords: Internet, e-banking, Cyber Security, Privacy

Introduction

Online banking systems have become quite popular in the last ten years. It is an online payment system that enables different customers to conduct online financial transactions on a website. Customers from an online bank can manage their accounts with their own electronic devices as long as an Internet connection is available. Online banking is also referred as e-banking, virtual banking, Internet banking and by other terms.

Internet banking has proved to be an ideal and profitable means of banking in the banking industry. Most banks have quickly migrated to this technology in order to reduce cost and improve customer experience.

The process of adoption of technology depends on information gathering and set of belief that will help the user in either accepting or rejecting it. The technology acceptance determines that the user acceptance of technology is driven by two factors namely ease of using that technology and usefulness of the technology. Adoption of technology is the greatest challenge for the

banking industry. Some of the risk associated with the Internet banking users are users themselves; their behaviour when it comes to E-banking.

Internet banking security risk can cause financial losses if the risk is real. Financial sectors and banking sectors are more prone to security attacks. User acceptance is one of the key factors in the acceptance of technology. To work on Internet banking requires a certain level of information technology literacy. Users may not be comfortable in trusting a totally automated system.

Despite the fact that banks in emerging countries have integrated security features yet users' behaviour causes security vulnerabilities. A lot of internet security threats and vulnerabilities still continue to persist. An example is Internet banking users sharing their login credentials with others knowingly or unknowingly. This may lead to compromising of the user account and may lead to security breaches. As new threats continue to emerge, banks will need to adopt new measures to protect users.

Literature Review:

Review of literature is backbone of every research study. It is important to review the existing literature to have an overview of what kinds of studies have been conducted and what are the gaps in literature. Therefore, various studies in the domain of e-banking which were conducted in India and abroad have been reviewed.

Karjaluoto et.al, (2002) explored the effect of different factors in the attitude formation toward internet banking in Finland. For study purpose a sample of 1167 bank customers were taken. Attitude formation was studied with the help of Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The study found that prior experience & knowledge of computer and attitude toward computer influence attitude toward online banking. The study also found that demographic factors such as occupation and household income impact heavily on online banking behaviour.

Mattila et al., (2003) in their study analysed the mature customers' Internet banking behaviour in Finland. The survey sample consisted of three consumer segments (non-users, new users, old

users) that differed in terms of Internet banking experience and sample size was 1,167 bank customers. Household income and education were found to have a significant effect on the adoption of the Internet as a banking channel, so that over 30 percent of wealthy and well-educated mature males make e-banking their primary mode of making payments. Perceived difficulty in using computers combined with the lack of personal service in e-banking was found to be the main barriers of Internet banking adoption among mature customers. Internet banking was also found to be more unsecured among mature customers than bank customers in general.

Geeta (2003) reviewed the current scenario of phishing attacks in India and provided some countermeasures that can be adopted by online firms to fight this kind of attack. The study found that there has been an increase in identity theft in the last few years which could pose a serious problem in the future, resulting in loss of trust by the customer towards net banking. Most of the Indian banks are taking initiatives to address the problem but still more work is to be done in the case of small and rural banks. In the end, the study furnished guidelines to tackle the situation.

Gerrard et al., (2006) attempted to find out factor which were responsible for not using internet banking. For study purpose, a survey was used to acquire data from 127 consumers who were not internet user. Using a content analysis procedure, eight factors were identified which explain why consumers were not using internet banking. 67 the identified factors were perceptions about risk; the need; lacking knowledge; inertia; inaccessibility; human touch; pricing and IT fatigue.

Celik, Hakan (2008) in his study provided an insight into the determinants of customers 'acceptance to internet banking. The study has addressed a research need 69 for extending the technology acceptance model (TAM) by adding contextual factors for the case of Internet banking. The additional contextual factors added to model were perceived behavioural control (PBC), perceived playfulness (PPL) and perceived risk (PR). The partial least squares (PLS) procedure is used to analyse 161 cases collected from individual Internet banking users through a web-based survey. The results indicated that perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) are immediate direct determinants of customers 'attitudes towards using Internet banking. PU, PR and ATT determine the large proportion of behavioural intentions to use Internet banking. Although PPL positively influences only PEOU, PBC exerts positive direct effects on PEOU and PU and indirect effects on PU and ATT. Study also found that Perceived

Risk i.e., concern for security and privacy could be one of the obstacles for IB adoption and its adverse effects should not be underestimated by practitioners.

Kesharwani and Bisht (2012) attempted to extend the technology acceptance model (TAM) in the context of internet banking adoption in India under security and privacy threat. The study revealed that perceived risk had a negative impact on behavioral intention of internet banking adoption and trust had a negative impact on perceived risk. A well-designed web site was also found to be helpful in facilitating easier use and also minimizing perceived risk concerns regarding internet banking usage. (Kumar et.al.2022)

Research Problem

What are the different aspects of Cyber Securities in E-Banking Services from Customers' perspectives?

Research objective:

The study was conducted with following objectives: -

- To analyse the customers' perceptions and awareness towards Internet banking security
- To understand the problems faced by customers while using internet banking services
- To know impact of the internet banking securities among the selected customers
- To study the security & privacy issues and regulatory environment of e-banking services in India.
- To find out the relationship between security & privacy concern and security & privacy satisfaction.
- To understand the opinion of non-users of e-banking services.

Research methodology:

- This is Descriptive research. The present study examines the security and privacy issues in e-banking. With a view to develop a sound theoretical framework for investigation, review of literature in related to e-banking services and security issues has been carried out.

Important studies related to adoption of e-banking services, security issues in e-banking services etc. conducted have been reviewed.

- Population, Sampling and Sample Size- The population for the study comprised of customers of selected private sector banks . For study purpose, four banks of private sector were selected i.e., ICICI, AXIS,HDFC,KOTAK. More specifically, the target population for the study was defined as —Bank customers who have used at least one e-banking service two times in the last quarter.
- The prime objective of the study was to examine the perception of bank customers regarding security and privacy concern in selected banks. Therefore, a sample of 100 bank customers divided equally among selected banks was planned. However, the researcher could obtain only 57 valid questionnaires. Thus, the findings of this study are based on opinion of 57 respondents.
- Sampling Unit: Sampling unit for data collection was individual bank customers.
- Instruments Design: To collect the data from bank customers, a structured questionnaire was prepared. The questionnaire was prepared in consultation with Dr.Atul Kumar. Researcher also took into account the inputs of e-banking users to include important aspects of e-banking security in the questionnaire.
- The first part of the questionnaire dealt with the demographic profile of the respondents.
- The second part of the questionnaire consisted of eight constructs which were used to measure the level of security & privacy concern and level of satisfaction regarding security & privacy concerns of e-banking services. Respondents were asked to indicate their opinion on Five-Point Likert Scale ranging from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree”.

Research design

A research design is the overall plan for obtaining answers to the questions being studied and for handling some of the difficulties encountered during the research process. The main purpose behind the study was to know the awareness and customers perception regarding the cyber threats related to e banking.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

1.	Name of your bank?	Respondents
	AXIS	48
	ICICI	60
	HDFC	88
	KOTAK	32
	TOTAL	228

2.	Educational Qualification-	Respondents
	Undergraduate	64
	Graduate	80
	Post-Graduate	32
	Others	52
	TOTAL	228

3.	Age	Respondents
	<25	80
	<35	68
	<50	48
	>50	32
	TOTAL	228

4.	Gender	Respondents
	Male	160
	Female	68
	Others	-
	TOTAL	228

5.	Occupation	Respondents
	Professional	60
	Business	80
	Housewife	8
	Student	80
	TOTAL	228

6.	Which of the following new technology-based banking channels are you aware?	YES	NO
	Internet Banking	92	22
	Mobile Banking	98	16
	Phone Banking	70	24
	Total	260	62

7.	Do you use Internet Banking?	YES	NO
	Respondents	192	44

8.	How often do you use?	Respondents
	More than once a week	144
	Once in a week	44
	Once in a fortnight	20
	Once in a month	20

9.	For what purpose do you internet banking?	Yes	No
	Checking Balance	120	108
	Transfer of Funds	160	68
	Payment of Bills	208	20
	Online Shopping	188	40

10.	Which of the security feature(s) of internet banking are you aware of?	Yes	No
	One Time Password (OTP)	108	8
	Profile Password	68	188
	PIN	20	28

No. 11	Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Is agree	Strongly Disagree
	It is safe to use internet banking of my bank	80	40	0	60	8
	My internet banking password may be stolen	60	0	28	80	40
	Funds may be fraudulently transferred from my account to other's account	20	40	60	80	28
	One can monitor my financial transaction history	40	60	80	20	28
	Bank will not refund my money back if there is online fraud	60	60	80	28	0
	Internet banking is vulnerable to fraud	80	60	0	40	40
	The site provides security guidelines on home page	28	40	8	60	40
	OTP (One Time Password) is required, if logging from different browsers/computers	60	80	60	60	8
	Bank remind me to change password from time to time	44	24	20	80	28
	Bank provide me the facility of choosing strong password for internet banking	60	60	52	8	28

12.	Please rate you overall satisfaction about the Internet banking services of your principal bank.	Respondents
	Highly Satisfied	80
	Satisfied	80
	Neutral	40
	Dissatisfied	28

Conclusion

Here it can be concluded that around 70 % of people have positive perception & are satisfactory with E-Banking Services. Still people of these areas are not using all the E-banking services frequently because they less knowledge about computer and internet; so they feel hesitation in using E-banking services. So banks should improve their promotional and communication strategies to make aware the customers regarding IT services and build-up positive perception to improve the level of usage of E-Banking with high level of satisfaction.

At present Indian banks are investing huge amount in the infrastructure to host internet banking activities. However, adoption rate of e-banking services is very low in India as compared to developed countries. Various research studies showed that apart from other factors concern for securities and privacy is most important factor influencing the adoption of internet banking. The present study also found that except ATM, the level of concern for security and privacy regarding use of e-banking services is high. In this context, the findings of the study have implications for banking industry in two ways. Firstly, the comparison of security and privacy features will help the bankers to make their online portal more secure by incorporating the security features which other banks are using. Secondly, the study will be helpful to the bankers to understand the behavior of internet banking users and behaviour of non-internet banking users. It will help bankers to understand the security and privacy aspect of various e-banking services

where customers have high level of concern. It will assist the bankers to retain the existing bank customer and to convert the potential users to actual e- banking users.

References:

Books, Journals, Reports, Newspapers-:

1. Celik, Hakan (2008), _What determines Turkish customers 'acceptance of internet banking? ', International Journal of Bank Marketing, Vol. 26 No. 5, pp. 353- 370.
2. Geeta, D. Vijay (2011), _Online identity theft – an Indian perspective ', Journal of Financial Crime, Vol. 18 No. 3, pp. 235-246.
3. Gerrard, Philip, Cunningham, J., Barton, Devlin, James F. (2006), _Why consumers are not using internet banking: a qualitative study ', Journal of Services Marketing, Vol.20 No.3, pp.160–16.
4. KarjaluotoHeikki, Mattila Minna and PentoTapio (2002), Factor underlying attitude formation towards online banking in Finland ', International Journal of Bank Marketing, Vol.20 No. 6, 261-272.
5. Kesharwani, Ankit and Bisht, Shailendra Singh (2012), _The impact of trust and perceived risk internet banking adoption in India: An extension of technology acceptance model ', International Journal of Bank Marketing, Vol. 30 No. 4, 2012, pp. 303-322.
6. Kumar, A., Joshi, J., &Saxena, J. (2018). Service portfolio analysis of banking sector: A comparative study. MERC Global's International Journal of Management, 6(4), 168-174
7. Kumar, A., Tiwari, A., Mantri, J., & Chakraborty, D. (2022). Study of customer aspects of cyber securities in e-banking. In Proceedings of Global Educational Leadership Conference (pp. 86-97). Mumbai; Bestow Edutrex Int. LLP.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6612834>
8. Mattila, Minna, Karjaluoto, Heikki and Pento, Tapio (2003), Internet banking adoption among mature customers: early majority or laggards? 'Journal of Services Marketing, Vol. 17 No. 5, pp. 514-528.

VICMR 2022 PROCEEDINGS

Editors:

Dr. ATUL KUMAR
Dr. A. VETRI SELVI
Dr. A. GANDHI
Dr. R. VIJAYALAKSHMI
Dr. J. MADHUSUDHANAN

Associate Editors:

Dr. G.S. JAYESH
Dr. K. KRISHNAVENI
Dr. SAJITH
Dr. V. JEYANTHI KUMARI
Dr. IRFAN ABDUL KARIM SHAIKH

Published by

Saliha Publications

Tamil Nadu, INDIA

<https://salihapublications.wordpress.com/>
E. mail: salihapublications2016@gmail.com
Cell: +91 8667862635.

ISBN: 978-93-94198-04-3